

中国典型培养物保藏中心

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Entrusted by Zhejiang University, CCTCC has conducted identification experiments on the BxPC-M8 cell line, and come to the following conclusions:

1. There was no third allele found in all the locations of BxPC-M8 cell line, it indicating that there was no cross-contaminant of human source cell line.
2. Compared the STR data of BxPC-M8 cell line in the databases of ATCC, DSMZ and JCRB, all the locations of BxPC-M8 were exactly matched with the locations of BxPC-3 cells found in all the three cell banks, so it is BxPC-3 cell line (Table 1).

Director's Signature:

China Center for Type Culture Collection

Table 1. The alleles of 21 locations in BxPC-M8 cell line

BxPC-M8 cell line (Fig. No.XB4162)		
Marker	Allele 1	Allele 2
D19S433	13	16.2
D5S818	11	11
D21S11	29	29
D18S51	12	12
D6S1043	12	12
AMEL	X	X
D3S1358	14	16
D13S317	11	11
D7S820	10	13
D16S539	9	11
CSF1PO	13	13
Penta D	14	14
D2S441	12	14
vWA	14	18
D8S1179	13	13
TPOX	8	8
Penta E	12	14
TH01	9	9
D12S391	19.3	20
D2S1338	17	19
FGA	20	21